

Constructive Mathematics, Quantum mechanics, Free Will and Consciousness

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November 30, 2020

Abstract

The objective of this paper is to show that non-constructive mathematics is incapable as a framework for research on consciousness. Indeed, we shall discuss how non-constructive mathematics is inconsistent with physics of consciousness which deals with quantumness. This inconsistency implies the incapability of non-constructive mathematics to represent the free will of a conscious agent. Furthermore, we shall suggest Constructive mathematics (and topos theory which is one of its models) as an alternative framework to study consciousness. The pivotal role of the excluded middle law in our discussion will be addressed in detail.

Keywords: Constructive mathematics, Quantum Mechanics, Topos Theory, Excluded middle law, Free will and Consciousness

1 Introduction

Consciousness is not a simple topic to research and even to talk it over informally. Because it has a very strong relation with the meaning of *existence* which can be considered as the most fundamental and also trivial concept which is meaningful to our mind.

However, *Daniel C. Dennett school* which seems *the only game in town*, by *"hook or crook"*, and its materialistic consequences, has pushed scientists to discuss about the most trivial and fundamental concepts which are perceptible for us as *"conscious agents"*.

We agree with the philosophical position of *Mario Beauregard and Denyse O'Leary* on science which is mentioned in their book *The Spiritual Brain*. Unfortunately, science became a servant of *materialism* instead of a search for truth.[1]. We think the reason why for this deformation of science is a monopoly in scientific society which is *Daniel C. Dennett school* and we try to introduce a big class of philosophical and scientific methodologies in science, especially fields of study on consciousness, which are very far away from this school.

The majority of readers probably have heard this quotation: "ego cogito, ergo sum"; "I think, therefore I am" from René Descartes' *Principia Philosophiae*[2].¹ One may interpret this quotation in this way: Descartes used thinking to prove his existence, but we think the correct interpretation can be this one: I am equivalent with my thoughts. What is our reason for this claim? The answer is that as soon as we use the term *I think* literally we accepted our existence as a conscious individual. Thus, it can not be a reason for our existence, rather it is our existence itself. Consciousness is our existence and not a reason of it. *Consciousness is fundamental*.

Nevertheless, in this paper we do not want to take the above assumption. Instead we try to show that the way of research on the content of consciousness, *free will* and *qualia* is passing through the very heart of quantum physics and, non trivially, the domain of constructive mathematics(CM). Naturally, within a paper with this scope, we do not pursue pedagogical aims, but, since we guess our reader maybe are not necessarily familiar with constructive mathematics, we try to explain the building blocks of CM in a way that be understandable by majority of non-expert reader in this field.

¹Some people know this quotation in this form: "Cogito, ergo sum."

2 Why Consciousness is Indescribable Using Non-Constructive Mathematics?

In order to answer the above question, first of all we have to discuss the main notions of constructive mathematics and its differences with common non-constructive mathematics.

To pursue this aim, there are several roads and indeed, to introduce different schools of **CM**, a long historical discussion is needed. But this desirable historical travel is not possible here. Instead, we try to skip many really important arguments and just pick up a shortcut to describe the very heart of *CM*.

The next step is to explain the reason why that *CM* is needed to develop a consistent mathematical foundation of quantum mechanics while non-constructive mathematics(**NCM**) is highly problematic for this purpose.

2.1 Newtonian School Vs Leibniz School of Mathematics

Two giants of mathematics in the 17th century, *Isaac Newton* and *Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz* have had a large influence not only on human scientific career but also on his general way of thinking and philosophy.

Without *Calculus*, almost none of our achievements in *astronomy*, *aerospace science*, *mechanical engineering*, *modern medicine* and many other fields of science would have been possible.

Nevertheless, surprisingly among those scientists who know about the importance of the discoveries of *Newton* and *Leibniz*, just a very small minority are aware of the huge differences between the approaches of these two giants to the *calculus*.

The main *spring* of these huge differences is the notion of *infinitesimal*. In *Newtonian approach* of calculus, we have the common notion of *limit* and then the elements of calculus are built based on this notion, which in our opinion is an *unnatural notion*. However, we do not want to discuss the reason why this approach is not mathematically natural. Instead we refer the reader to [3], to gain valuable historical information about that.

We have strong reasons that the other approach to calculus which we call it *Leibniz school* is more natural, both logically and synthetically. Moreover, we will show that this school provides a consistent mathematical foundation of quantum mechanics(**QM**) and consequently(not trivially) a worth framework to research on conscious theory.

Let us introduce an elementary but formal definition of the notion of infinitesimal, which is sufficient for our discussion in the scope of this paper.

Definition 1 Suppose that R is a commutative ring. We set:

$$D := \{x \in R | x^2 = 0\}.$$

The elements of the set D are called *infinitesimals*.

More precisely these elements are *first ordered infinitesimals*, but for our aim in this text, this precision in naming is not important.

From algebraic point of view the elements of D are *nilpotent* elements of the ring R . It is clear that $D \subset R$. In *Leibniz school* we assume that $D \neq \{0\}$, thus R can not be regarded as the field of real number \mathbb{R} .

Roughly speaking, $D \neq \{0\}$, guarantees the *existence* of some elements in R like x which are not equal to zero, but are extremely small such that: $x^2 = 0$.

There are several philosophical arguments about the existence of infinitesimals among mathematicians, even our contemporary mathematicians. Among them, the ideas of French *Fields medallist* mathematician, *Alain Connes*, are very important, due to the connection of these ideas with *non commutative geometry*(**NCG**). We refer the reader to see [4] to find some interesting and absolutely serious discussions about recent issue.

Since now, it is desirable for us to emphasize the hidden role of the word existence in our discussion. We think, *the act of* making decision about *existence or inexistence* of a logically definable mathematical notion is a very clear sign of the fact that *mathematics is subjective*. We have a similar claim about theoretical physics as a science and humanistic activity which that shall become bold when we look at very heart of quantum mechanics.

Differential geometry(**DG**) which is based on the notion of smoothness and more primarily the notion of limit in calculus is a very well-known branch of mathematics and from this point of view it belongs to the *Newtonian school*. However from another aspect, which is related to the notion of space with *locally Euclidean* feature instead of *globally Euclidean*, *DG* does not belong to the *Newtonian school*.

DG is the most important geometrical tool to study the *general relativity*. Furthermore, *DG* beside other mathematical tools as like as *category theory*, *cobordisms theory*, *algebraic geometry* and *homological algebra* makes the mathematical framework of research on both serious approaches to *quantum gravity*, which are *string theory* and *loop quantum gravity*.

In the following, using the notion of infinitesimal (instead of notion of limit), we will introduce the main axiom of *synthetic differential geometry*(**SDG**) which is the analogue of *DG* in *Leibniz school*. This axiom is called **Kock-Lawvere axiom**, and is formulated as follows:

$$\forall g \in R^D, \exists ! b \in R, \forall d \in D : g(d) = g(0) + d \cdot b$$

where $g \in R^D$ means g is a function from D to the R . See[3].

Here, we need to introduce the *law of excluded middle* to see its pivotal role in shaping radically different schools of mathematics and then, to see that it is necessary to exclude this law to study on quantum mechanics and consciousness.

Definition 2 *The Law of Excluded Middle*(LEM): For any logical proposition p either p is true or $\neg p$ is true. By $\neg p$ we mean the negation of p .

One can clearly see that *LEM* is coming from a *Boolean logic* point of view, spectacles of *Zero or one, to be or not to be, live or dead*. However *QM* is a theory which logically is not Boolean at all. We shall discuss this fact later.

Proposition 1 *The Kock-Lawvere axiom is not compatible with the law of excluded middle.*

For a proof see [3].

This theorem suggests that we should exclude *LEM* from our mathematical foundation if we want to be permitted to talk about infinitesimals. We need *D* does not contain only zero. We need infinitesimals to use *Kock-Lawvere* axiom. Hence, in *Leibniz school*, the law of excluded middle does not exist.

Proposition 2 *The axiom of choice implies the law of excluded middle.*

We refer the reader to [3], for a proof. This proposition suggests another exclusion. In the framework of constructive mathematics and *Leibniz school* we reject the validity of *the axiom of choice*.

2.2 Why Quantum Mechanics and Consciousness Theory need Leibniz School?

What is *consciousness* and how does it manifest any meaningful form of our *free will* as *conscious agents*?

Here, we want to clarify our point of view about possible ways of dealing with this question.

Terminologically, we do not use the term *consciousness* in the same meaning as *intelligence* or *awareness*. However, we believe that consciousness has a close bilateral relationship with both of these concepts. Consciousness generates awareness using a *hierarchical qualitative (and in some frameworks quantitative) ability of paying attention* which we call *intelligence*, then this generated awareness induces a new state of consciousness.

We assume, consciousness is the "*cause*" of our brains activities those to provide the cognitive ability of recognizing our individual "*I*"s (or *egos*). In this case, we follow similarly *monistic* philosophical choice which *D.D. Hoffman* and *Chetan Prakash* have chosen in their theory of consciousness. We refer the reader to see [5] to learn about this philosophical attitude.

Therefore, we do not assume that consciousness is generated probably by "*reticular formation*" or by any other certain neuronal activities in the brain. Instead, we assume that the *casual force* comes from the consciousness and then brain monitors and implements its functions and content using various neuronal activities (in this case, maybe neuronal activities of reticular formation).

In addition, we should mention that the term *conscious agents* which is used in this paper is taken from [5], however in our point of view the dynamics of conscious agents should be described in a framework of constructive mathematics to be consistent with quantum theory. It will be the topic of further research.

After the above discussion about terminology and the meaning of consciousness, we now discuss the dependence of consciousness and free will of conscious agents.

In this text, we define "free will" as *the possible hierarchical liberation or freedom of a conscious agent to select its own private way to interact with the universe, contains the spectrum of interactions from the most abstract levels of thinking to the possibly any physical interaction with environment.*

Based on our definition of free will, those who are familiar with "quantum bayesianism" and its radical form "QBism", may guess that we suppose to use QBism as an interpretation of quantum mechanics in our discussion on consciousness. Although this guess is pretty correct, but QBism as what we have in mind about it, has some differences with its original and accepted form which is described in [6].

According to our definition of *free will*, it is an element of the content of consciousness. Essentially, manifestation of the consciousness of a conscious agent happens in the frames of two basic phenomena: *Qualia* and *free will*.

But one may ask this question: "Is it possible to consider *free will* for a conscious agent in a *Newtonian (or Laplacian) deterministic universe*?" Our reply to this question is "No" strongly. The reason is that a deterministic world², as *Christopher Fuchs* argues in [6], is metaphorically "a written book from beginning to end" and if this is the case, then an imaginary *omniscient being* knows everything about all conscious agents. In another words, in a deterministic world there is no place for free will, because every act of a conscious agent eventually is predictable not probabilistically but analytically. We have a quite different point of view about the notion of "omniscient being" which is the source of the differences between QBism in its original and accepted form and our point of view. We think the existence or inexistence of an *omniscient being* (or more of them) can discuss regardless of indeterminism of the world. The root of this claim is deeply entangled with the meaning of a "thing". We may discuss this case later.

Up to now, we discussed the reason why that free will has no meaning in a deterministic world. Since we have quantum mechanics in hand, one may clearly see that our world is not a deterministic one. Quantum mechanics rejects the idea of a deterministic world and *Kochen–Specker theorem* excludes any theory of *hidden variables*. Hence, a cognitive scientist should see the role of what we call "quantumness" in any discussion about consciousness, and one of the elements of its content which is free will. Otherwise, without any further assumption and discussion, one will arrive to the paradoxical situation of making

²We hope the reader recognized that here we preferred to not use the word universe. The reason is that in framework of QBism, essentially the word Universe=Uni+verse can not carry out the main meaning of QBism. Instead, a "QBist" prefer the word "pluriverse" for talking about our world. See [6]

a liberate indeterministic choice in a deterministic world.

It remains to clarify that quantum mechanics needs *Leibniz school*. Indeed, the law of excluded middle (definition 2) plays a pivotal role here. To pursue this aim, let us recall the *axioms of quantum mechanics*:

1. We assume that a Hilbert space is associated with any isolated physical system and we call this Hilbert space, *state space of the system*. A system is completely described by its state vector, which is a unit vector in the state space of the system.
2. The evolution of an isolated (closed) quantum system is described by a unitary transformation. The time evolution of the state of an isolated quantum system is described by the *Schrödinger's equation* as follows:

$$i\hbar \frac{d|\psi\rangle}{dt} = H|\psi\rangle.$$

In this equation \hbar is a physical constant known as Planck's constant.

3. Quantum measurements are described by a collection M_m of measurement operators. The index m refers to the measurement outcomes that may occur in the experiment. These are operators acting on the state space of the system being measured. If the state of the quantum system is $|\psi\rangle$ immediately before the measurement then the probability that result m occurs is given by:

$$p(m) = \langle \psi | M_m^\dagger M_m | \psi \rangle$$

Where $p(m) = \langle \psi | M_m^\dagger M_m | \psi \rangle$ is inner product of $|\psi\rangle$ and $M_m^\dagger M_m | \psi \rangle$.

Since according to the axioms of probability theory, a quantum system must be in one of the possible states after the act of measurement (for instance, a dice after dropping should be in one state between 1 and 6) the measurement operators should satisfy the completeness condition:

$$\sum_m p(m) = \sum_m \langle \psi | M_m^\dagger M_m | \psi \rangle = 1.$$

Axiom 3 is at the root various different Interpretations of quantum mechanics, because it shows the role of the rest of world (with respect to the closed quantum system) i.e. the environment, and its interaction with the quantum system which includes the measurement process performed by the observer.

4. *The superposition principle*. This principle states that if $|x\rangle$ and $|y\rangle$ are two states of a quantum system, then any *superposition* $\alpha|x\rangle + \beta|y\rangle$ should also be an allowed state of the quantum system, where $\alpha^2 + \beta^2 = 1$. See [7, 8].

Here we are dealing specifically with the 4th axiom which is the *superposition principle*. This axiom seems very counter-intuitive to our minds. Indeed, the problem with *Newtonian School* has started from this point. In the *Newtonian school* of mathematics the law of excluded middle is held, hence if, using *Schrödinger's cat* scenario, we pick up the following oppositional states $|alive\rangle$ and $|dead\rangle$, then there is no more valid state in Newtonian context.

In another words, underlying logic of *Newtonian school* of mathematics and more specifically the law of excluded middle is inconsistent with the notion of superposition. In contrast, underlying logic of *Leibniz school* is perfectly consistent to the notion of superposition. Since in this school the law of excluded middle is not valid, hence we can write down a superposed state $|alive\rangle + |dead\rangle$ for *Schrödinger's cat*.

From a "*toposopher's*"³ point of view, this fact is related to internal logic of a chosen *topos* which is not equivalent with topos of sets. In another word, *Newtonian school* is based on the Boolean topos of sets, while *Leibniz school* is based on a very richer non-Boolean topos. We refer the interested reader to [9] for learn about the topos theory. Overall, we have clarified that the correct and consistent mathematical foundation of quantum mechanics is constructive mathematics and *Leibniz school*. The inconsistency of the notion of superposition with the underlying logic of Newtonian school may be ignorable. Physicists usually accept this notion as a counter-intuitive notion and continue their career. But in proceed, more problematic situations and paradoxes will appear in modern physics, as they have already appeared. One class of them is some problems in foundations of string theory, for instance *T-duality* which forced some physicists to think about more counter-intuitive ideas such as *mirror symmetry*.

Finally, we recall that one of the most well-known and applicable model of constructive mathematics is *topos theory*. Developing a topos theoretical framework of QM has been the topic of some works by *Andreas Döring* and *Chris Isham* (For instance see [10]) and we think there is a long road still to achieve this goal. Moreover, here we have shown that not only QM but also consciousness theory needs a topos theoretical framework which can be regarded as its mathematical foundation.

3 Debate of Constructivist and Existentialist on "Observing The Observer" and the Role of the Conscious Agent

The title of this section contains the main title of two serial papers of *Vlatko Vedral*, "*Observing the Observer*". See [11] and [12].

Since these two papers are very short and clear, we do not want to paraphrase anything from there. Instead, let us just quote from V.Vedral and then start

³The term "*toposopher*" for the first time is suggested by the famous algebraic geometer *Miles Ried*. See [9]

our discussion.

”The idea that quantum mechanics applies to everything in the universe, even to us humans, can lead to some interesting conclusions.” [11]

This is the first quotation which we need here. The second quotation is his scenario of a thought experiment. This scenario is as follows.

”Suppose that a very able experimental physicist, Alice, puts her friend Bob inside a room with a cat, a radioactive atom and cat poison that gets released if the atom decays. The point of having a human there is that we can communicate with him. As far as Alice is concerned, the atom enters into a state of being both decayed and not decayed, so that the cat is both dead and alive (that’s where Schrodinger stops). Bob, however, can directly observe the cat and sees it as one or the other. This is something we know from everyday experience: we never see dead and alive cats. To confirm this, Alice slips a piece of paper under the door asking Bob whether the cat is in a definite state. He answers, “Yes, I see a definite state of the cat”. At this point, mathematically speaking, the state of the system has changed from the initial state

$$|\psi_i\rangle = |no - decay\rangle |\text{poison in the bottle}\rangle \\ |\text{cat alive}\rangle |\text{Bob sees alive cat}\rangle |\text{blank piece of paper}\rangle$$

to the state (from Alice’s global perspective):

$$|\psi_{1/2}\rangle = (|\text{decay}\rangle |\text{poison released}\rangle |\text{cat dead}\rangle |\text{Bob sees dead cat}\rangle \\ + |\text{no-decay}\rangle |\text{poison still in the bottle}\rangle |\text{cat alive}\rangle \\ |\text{Bob sees alive cat}\rangle) \\ \otimes |\text{paper says: yes, I see a definite state of the cat}\rangle$$

I am assuming that, because Alice’s laboratory is isolated, every transformation leading up to this state is unitary. This includes the decay, the poison release, the killing of the cat and Bob’s observation - Alice has a perfect quantum coherent control of the experiment. Note that Alice does not ask whether the cat is dead or alive because for her that would force the outcome or, as some physicists might say, “collapse the state (this is exactly what happens in Wigner’s version, where he communicates the state to a friend, who communicates to another friend and so on...). She is content observing that Bob sees the cat either alive or dead and does not ask which it is. Because Alice avoided collapsing the state (in other words, she did not get entangled to her experiment), quantum theory holds that slipping

the paper under the door was a reversible act. She can undo all the steps she took since each of them is just a unitary transformation. In other words, the paper itself also does not get entangled to the rest of the laboratory. When Alice reverses the evolution, if the cat was dead, it would now be alive, the poison would be in the bottle, the particle would not have decayed and Bob would have no memory of ever seeing a dead cat. If the cat was alive, it would also come back to the same state (everything, in other words, comes back to the starting state where the atom has not decayed, the poison is in the bottle, the cat is alive and Bob sees alive cat and has no memory of the experiment he was subjected to). And yet one trace remains: the piece of paper saying “yes, I see a definite state of the cat”. Alice can undo Bob’s observation in a way that does not also undo the writing on the paper. The paper remains as proof that Bob had observed the cat as definitely alive or dead half way through the experiment. (Note that I remain interpretation neutral. A Many Worlds supporter would say that there are two copies of Bob, one that observes a dead cat and one that sees alive cat; a Copenhagen or Quantum Bayesian supporter could say that relative to one state of Bob the cat is dead, while, relative to the other, it is alive - either way, supporters of any interpretation ought to make the same predictions in this experiment).” See [12].

This is where he stopped in his first paper and...!. We refer the interested reader to see [11] and then [12] to see what he did in continue. At the end of this section, we decide to do the same act as what he has done immediately after his stop.

After these two quotations, we have the needed elements of our discussion in hand. First of all, as one can see, the subject of the first quotation contains us, human being, and we like it even if the author himself be regret to emphasize human, there.

Secondly, the main elements of our discussion on the”Vedral’s scenario”⁴ are as following.

- 1 . The nature of *Bob’s mind*, While Bob can be regarded as an element of a spectrum of conscious agents which contains the most primitive shapes of conscious agents(For instance a mirror) up to the AI and finally humans.
- 2 . The way that Alice do questioning from Bob. As one can see in the quotation, Alice does not ask whether the cat is dead or alive because for her that would force the outcome or, as some physicists might say, “collapse the state (this is exactly what happens in Wigner’s version, where he communicates the state to a friend, who communicates to another friend

⁴As Vedral has mentioned himself in his papers [11] and [12], this scenario is built based on Deutsch’s variant [13] of the Schrodinger cat thought experiment that builds on Wigner’s ideas.

Figure 1: Kanisza Triangle

and so on...). Instead, she slips a piece of paper under the door asking Bob whether the cat is in a definite state.

We agree with the conclusions of the paper and as well we think taking QM into account just about sub-atomic or microscopic world is a mainstream mistake. We believe quantum mechanics is applicable to everything in the universe, as *Vedral* claims correctly. However, it can lead to some startling conclusions,

Also, we reply "yes" to the question in title of second serial paper [12]. But our "yes" perhaps is a tricky yes. I may know that I am in a superposition and still be in a superposition, but it depends on "who I am" and what is *knowing* here precisely. What is the difference of knowing and *feeling* here. We believe that these are not philosophical questions any more. These questions can be regarded as scientific questions now (maybe a very important class of scientific questions), however, at least author of this paper has not any problem if someone likes to verbalize them philosophical.

We can feel something and do not know what it is exactly. Even, we may experience a feeling of knowing something while we do not know what we really know. Necker cube is a very nice tool in order to discuss the different states of mind and consciousness. *Vedral* has used it in his argument [12]. We pick up another nice tool which is called *Kanisza triangle* (*Gaetano Kanizsa*, 1976) to discuss states of consciousness and its content. See the figure 1.

When you are looking at Kanisza triangle, you may simply see a white triangle. Indeed, you may see a white triangle which does not exist. Your consciousness reconstructs it. Our consciousness using two tricks of *binding* and *closure*, reconstruct a white triangle for you within your mind. This is your *qualia*, your first person experience. Thus, your visual perception is not so precise and honest as you may think. D.D. Hoffman is an expert of visual perception, therefore we refer the reader to see [14] to learn more about our visual perception. There are many examples in [14] which express that we do not perceive reality as it is. Thus, before listening to the debate that we advertised it in the title of this section, you may consider some existentialistic problems which play a very tricky role in our discussion. Despite *Newtonian world*, in *QM's world*, Ontology is equivalent to epistemology. For a constructivist it is the case too.

Since now, the author of this paper is in a debate as a constructivist with the nickname "Oracle" with an existentialist with the nickname "Jean". We excluded the non-constructive mathematician from this debate by our argument in previous section. The reason for presence of Jean as an existentialist in this debate is the similarity of his mindset with a non-constructive mathematician in some philosophical aspects and his probably neutral position about mathematical framework and underlying mathematical logic of discussion.

The moderator of this debate is an independent thinker with no nickname and probably a fan of Oracle. This debate is not like common political debates. Thus, here psychologically, nobody has this mindset that learning is equivalent with losing or convincing the others is winning. Instead, both sides are trying to understand the truth. The debate is as following.

Moderator: Why the nature of the Bob's mind does matter in Vedral's scenario?

Jean: In my opinion, the only important concern about the Bob's mind is its capability to communicate with Alice and maybe one can replace it with an *artificial intelligence* (AI) in Vedral's scenario and there is no problem. However I have doubt about the existence of a real AI.

Oracle: In think, the nature of Bob's mind might not change anything about the startling conclusion of the Vedral's scenario, but considering different state of consciousness may show us how much still we are far away from understanding of QM. This is not related to the different interpretations of QM, instead, I think it is related to our understanding from *the meaning of an interpretation* itself which is limited because of our hidden and unconsciousness non-constructive mathematical pre-assumption. To start, I suggest to be more flexible about the nature of Bob's mind. Let us consider a spectrum of conscious agents contains the most primitive shapes of them, up to AI (The Emperor's New Clothes) ⁵ and eventually human's mind ⁶. For instance, in the first step we can pick up a mirror to play the role of the Bob (and even another mirror for cat) and regard it as a *one-bit agent* which is a representative of the class of the most elementary conscious agents having just two experiences and two actions. See [14] to learn more about this primitive shape of conscious agents. Mirror's two experiences are recoil and not recoil (stay still).[12]

Moderator: I am not a good moderator. Oracle is talking more than Jean. I am not a fair coin and even not a fit representative of the mentioned class of one-bit agents(Here, imaginary audiences are try to show that they are intelligent by artificial histrionic laughing). Jean please, that is your turn.

⁵The Emperor's New Clothes is a story written by Danish author *Hans Christian Andersen*

⁶However, we still think that it is better to do not use mind and consciousness with the same meaning, but let us do it in order to simplicity and having more variety of vocabularies in this text.

Jean: I would like to ask Oracle that what do you mean when you say, we have misunderstanding about the meaning of an interpretation. I think it is clear to almost all of the philosophers and mathematicians that, in every arbitrary theory, propositions, statements and transcendental notions need something that is called interpretation to pass the process of signification and to become meaningful. Do you have any problem with this description of an interpretation?

Oracle: You know, I am a constructivist and for me, almost everywhere there is a middle case to reply, a yes or no question, which is "*yes and no at the same time*", but just whenever you accept my constructive mathematical position about time. Yes or no at the same time, for me, means the two different states of consciousness which are in coherency during 10^{-44} seconds (*Planck time*) or more, while shorter time *interval* does not exist. Practically, I may be happy with a *zeptosecond* (10^{-21} seconds). Back to your question, my answer is no, I have not problem with what you told about interpretation but when we are talking about something as like as QM then I have problem with the term meaningful. For a non-constructivist mathematician who believes in the law of excluded middle (*LEM*), the notion of superposition can never pass a process of significance. Thus, if you have found one of them who says that "I agree that a cat (or an electron) can be in a superposition state of dead and alive" then, there are only two cases: The first case is that he or she does not understand what is a superposition state, the second one is that she or he hides herself or himself behind a quantum physicists formalism and is not aware that this formalism is not consistence with the foundation of his mathematical formalism (set theoretical or any other type of non-constructive mathematical formalisms). I think QM is never understood correctly because the majority of physicists never rethink about its mathematical foundation. If it was not the case, now we had a better understanding of QM and mathematics as well. QM needs and even suggests its own mathematical foundation. It is clearly a mathematical framework in the world of constructive mathematics.

Moderator: Let me come back to the one-bit conscious agent, the mirror. I am so curious about it. How may you think that one-bit conscious agent can change the meaning of the content and conclusion of Vedral's scenario? and what about AI? Please Oracle, because you mentioned this class of conscious agents.

Oracle: I think there is no difference between a mirror, an AI, a coin and a real human with nickname Bob, *if they all obey the same rules of reasoning of non-constructive mathematics*. If our guest AI or Mr. Bob use excluded middle law to report their observation to Alice, then Alice can save her money and put a mirror inside the room instead of them. (Anyway, AIs are expensive still and even Mr. Bob as a friend needs at least lunch at the day of experiment). This is the hidden motivation of Alice to play

with our natural language to avoid collapsing the superposition state. Unconsciously, she assumed that Mr.Bob or AI are in the class of one-bit conscious agents in at the position of observer in this experiment and have only two possible experiences in their mind, see the alive cat, see the dead cat. It is possible that even Alice has this consideration about herself.

Jean: Oracle, let me interrupt you, the moderator slept and the audiences are waiting for coffee break enthusiastically. But, Alice knows that there is no other possibility for them. Moreover, maybe she is a *many world* supporter and thus she can consider two copy of Bob who coexist and report different results of observation. What you think?

Oracle: Thanks to the moderator and interested audiences, I can say liberally that with Alice mathematical and more fundamentally logical pre-assumption, Alice has not use any interpretation, she can stand in a interpretation-free position. Vedral, the creator of Alice, stood in this position, for a big part of his papers, [11] and [12]. I think since QBism has weaker ontological assumptions, it is a better interpretation of QM. It is practically much more easier to implementing this experiment and theoretically much more fruitful, if Alice be a QBist. In this case, she can ask a neurologist to do a quite simple surgery on Mr.Bob's brain and cut his *corpus callosum*((Corpus callosotomy)) and then he will experience a *dual consciousness*(Bob is a friend of Alice and probably accepts this surgery by enthusiasm, specially because he knows Alice is a very able experimental physicist and she can undo almost everything, specially his observation and probably she can glue his two brains hemisphere again, after the experiment, fortunately, but the paper will survive from this undo process, again fortunately.).

Moderator: Well, It was a wonderful debate(he is still sleepy but pretends that he was conscious at each moment of the debate). Time is over. It is time to have a coffee break.

We aware that many things remain to discuss. What is a thing?, see [10] and what is its importance to what we understand about QM? What is the position of a constructivist about the meaning of a thing and how does it affect our understanding of consciousness and QM? Many questions remain, but let us stop here and... . See the last sentence of [11].

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